

The Effect of Various Insufflation Pressures on Liver Function Test Postoperatively Following Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy means surgical removal of gallbladder based on minimally invasive approach utilizing the principle of pneumoperitoneum.

Objective: Objective of the study is to compare the outcome of high-pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy and low-pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy on liver function test in immediate post-operative period.

Materials and Methods: A prospective observational study of laparoscopic cholecystectomies performed during one year from May 2022 to April 2023 at Burdwan Medical College regarding the effect of various insufflation pressure on the changes seen in immediate post-operative liver function test.

Results: A total of 100 laparoscopic cholecystectomies were performed during the study period. The male to female ratio was 25:75 (1:3). 63% patients had previous episode of acute calculous cholecystitis, while 37% cases had incidental gallstone disease. All had radiologically confirmed gallstone disease. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was done and 1 hour postoperative liver function test was compared to preoperative liver function test after dividing patients in two groups; first group having laparoscopic cholecystectomy carried out at insufflation pressure of 10mmHg, and the other group having 14mmHg insufflation pressure. There was statistically significant difference between baseline and 1 hour postoperative values of serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin levels in patient undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy at 14mmHg insufflation pressure. Comparatively, patient undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy at 10mmHg insufflation pressure had no statistically significant difference between values of preoperative and postoperative levels of serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin. Serum alkaline phosphatase level showed no statistically significant difference in either of the two groups.

Conclusion: In our study, statistically significant increase in 1 hour postoperative values of serum total albumin, AST and ALT levels were seen compared to pre-insufflation values in group that underwent high pressure (14mmHg) laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The result show that 14mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum decreased blood flow to the liver and increased postoperative 1st hour AST, ALT and total bilirubin levels. It is therefore concluded that 10mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum is superior to 14mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Keywords: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy, Liver function test, Insufflation pressure, Pneumoperitoneum.

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Introduction

Chronic cholecystitis is a chronic condition caused by ongoing inflammation of the gall bladder resulting in inflammatory changes following mechanical or physiological dysfunction in its emptying. It presents as a smouldering course that can be accompanied by acute exacerbations of increased pain (acute biliary colic), or can progress to a more severe form of cholecystitis requiring urgent intervention. The two forms of chronic

cholecystitis are calculous (occurring in a setting of cholelithiasis), and acalculous (without gallstones). However, most cases of chronic cholecystitis are commonly associated with cholelithiasis. The epidemiology of chronic cholecystitis mostly parallels with that of cholelithiasis. About 10-20 percent of the world population develop gallstones at some point in their life and about 80 percent of them are asymptomatic. Risk factors for

cholelithiasis include female gender, obesity, rapid weight loss, pregnancy, advanced age and Hispanic or Pima Indian ethnicity. Cholecystectomy is one of the most commonly performed abdominal surgical procedures, and in developed countries many are performed laparoscopically. As an example, 90 percent of cholecystectomies in the United States are performed laparoscopically.[1]

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy came to the fore more than 30 years ago. The clinical practice of gallstone surgery has completely changed since then by the exponential growths of knowledge, skill, and technology; and it continues to evolve. It has now become the gold standard technique for gallbladder disease in both emergent and elective surgery. Nevertheless, there is neither a wide consensus on its related morbidity nor the factors determining associated complications.[2] A consensus statement on laparoscopic cholecystectomy was published more than a decade ago. [3] Several issues were addressed regarding the available evidence and clinical relevance of issues on how it shall be pursued in clinical practice. Several additional guidelines on it have emerged, including also emergent surgery and concomitant common bile duct interventions. [4] Indications for laparoscopic cholecystectomy are the same as those for open cholecystectomy-calculous/ acalculous cholecystitis (acute/chronic), biliary dyskinesia, gallstone pancreatitis, and gallbladder masses/ polyps. Although gallbladder cancer was once a contraindication to laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the current literature supports laparoscopic intervention.[5] Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is now considered “gold standard” for surgical treatment of gallstone disease. This procedure compared to open cholecystectomy results in lesser postoperative pain, better cosmesis, and shorter hospital stays and disability from work. Iatrogenic bile duct injury is always a possibility depending on the experience of the surgeon. While laparoscopic cholecystectomy is now the standard of care, patients should always be informed about the likelihood of conversion to an open procedure. The main aim of the study is to test the effects of various insufflation pressures on liver functions and to find out the safety of such operative procedures, especially in patients with underlying liver function abnormalities.

Aims and Objectives

Aims and Objective of this study is to compare the outcome of high-pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy and low-pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy on liver function test in immediate post-operative period. Aim of this study is also to assess the effect of high-pressure and low-pressure pneumoperitoneum on liver functions in the immediate post-operative period following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Purpose of this

study is to establish the safety of pneumoperitoneum in patients with pre-existing deranged liver functions and on patients undergoing long-duration surgery after analyzing all the data.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining consent from the Institutional Ethical Board, all the medical and surgical records obtained from the patient who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomies from May 2022 to April 2023 in Burdwan Medical College and Hospital were analysed. The study design was prospective observational study. All the data extracted includes age, sex, clinical presentation, preoperative investigations and trans-abdominal ultrasound. This study was conducted in 100 consecutive patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy who satisfied the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All the studied cases were subjected to clinical examination and abdominal ultrasound. Patients presented with clinical features and history suggestive of chronic cholecystitis attended in OPD of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital and who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Statistical Analysis

After compilation of all the collected data, analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 22 (IBM, Chicago, USA). As the study design was a prospective observational one, categorical variables are expressed as number of patients and percentage of patients with age wise distribution, sex predilection, clinical presentation and postoperative liver function test parameters one hour after laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Results

In our study period of one year (May 2022 to April 2023) total 100 laparoscopic cholecystectomies were performed. Of them, above the age of 40 were 49 and below the age of 40 were 51 (Figure1). Of the total patients involved in the study, 25 patients were male and 75 were female (1:3) (Figure 2). All of them presented to OPD with non-acute abdomen, with 63% having previous episode of acute calculous cholecystitis managed conservatively and 37% presenting after incidental diagnosis.

All the patients involved in the study were evaluated by taking detailed history and thorough clinical examination, followed by pre-anaesthetic check-up for operative fitness. They were then subjected to ultrasound abdomen to confirm the diagnosis of chronic calculous cholecystitis. All the 100 patients were radiologically confirmed to be having cholelithiasis. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was carried out and 1-hour

postoperative liver function test was compared to preoperative liver function test after dividing patient in 2 groups; first group having laparoscopic cholecystectomy carried out at insufflation pressure of 10 mmHg, and the other group having 14 mmHg insufflation pressure. Liver function test was focused on four parameters including total bilirubin level, serum AST, ALT and ALP levels.

The differences between the baseline and 1-hour postoperative values of serum AST (Figure 3), ALT (Figure 4) and total bilirubin levels (Figure 5) were statistically significant in the patients

undergoing standard 14 mmHg insufflation pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy, showing an increasing pattern. Comparatively, patients undergoing 10 mmHg insufflation pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy, there was no statistically significant difference between values of preoperative and postoperative liver function tests. Serum alkaline phosphatase levels (Figure 6) showed no statistically significant difference between preoperative and postoperative values in either of the two groups.

Pie Charts & Bar diagrams

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of chronic calculous cholecystitis in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Figure 2: Sex incidence of chronic calculous cholecystitis in patients needing laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Figure 3: Preoperative versus postoperative AST levels in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy (HPP: 14mmHg pneumoperitoneum; LPP: 10mmHg pneumoperitoneum)

Figure 4: Preoperative versus postoperative ALT levels in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy (HPP: 14mmHg pneumoperitoneum; LPP: 10mmHg pneumoperitoneum)

Figure 5: Preoperative versus postoperative total bilirubin levels in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy (HPP: 14mmHg pneumoperitoneum; LPP: 10mmHg pneumoperitoneum)

Figure 6: Preoperative versus postoperative total bilirubin levels in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy (HPP: 14mmHg pneumoperitoneum; LPP: 10mmHg pneumoperitoneum)

Discussion

Worldwide, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is most often performed by insufflating peritoneal cavity with CO₂. To provide good exposure of the surgical field, generally 10 to 15 mmHg pressure ranges are used during pneumoperitoneum. The effects of pneumoperitoneum on splanchnic and hepatic perfusion are not clearly understood. It was demonstrated in a pig model that intra-abdominal pressure greater than 12 mmHg may induce a reduction in splanchnic and hepatic perfusion.[6] In this study, the authors used one of three intraperitoneal pressures (8, 12, and 15 mmHg).

In another recent study, the authors installed intraabdominal pressure of 7 mmHg and 14 mmHg in healthy pigs and demonstrated that higher pressure decreases portal and superficial hepatic blood flow. They concluded that the derangement in the splanchnic compartment is dependent upon carbon dioxide pneumoperitoneum. It was demonstrated that an intra-abdominal pressure of less than 16 mmHg induces an increase in mesenteric artery and portal venous blood flow, due to local vasodilative effects of CO₂ on splanchnic vessels.[7] Intra-abdominal pressure of more than 16 mmHg is associated with a decrease in splanchnic perfusion.

Several previous studies reported the effects of pneumoperitoneum on splanchnic and liver perfusion. It was demonstrated that induction of CO₂ pneumoperitoneum with an insufflation pressure of 12 mmHg is associated with an increase in hepatic perfusion in healthy adults [8].

No definite explanation for these findings can be found. It was compared hepatic blood flow and function in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy with an intra-abdominal pressure

of 9–12 mmHg and concluded that laparoscopic cholecystectomy might impair hepatic function because of the high pressure. It was evaluated the effects of pneumoperitoneum on hepatic function in patients treated with laparoscopic procedures.[8]

The cholecystectomies were done with pneumoperitoneum at 10 mmHg and at 14 mmHg and found that all patients had a postoperative increase in AST and ALT levels. They suggested that patients with severe hepatic failure should probably not be subjected to prolonged laparoscopic procedures. In our study, we found an increase between baseline and postoperative 1st-hour serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin levels in Group II compared to Group I. Also, an increase was detected between the preoperative and postoperative 1st-hour serum alkaline phosphatase values, but no statistical difference was detected. The main reason for this change in liver physiology was due to high insufflation pressure.

In conclusion, the results show that 14 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum decreased the blood flow to the liver and increased postoperative 1st-hour serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin levels. It is therefore concluded that 10 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum is superior to 14 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Conclusion

The present study showed a statistically significant increase in 1-hour postoperative values of serum total bilirubin, AST and ALT levels compared to pre-insufflation values in group that underwent high pressure (14 mmHg) laparoscopic cholecystectomy. There was also rise in 1-hour postoperative serum alkaline phosphatase level compared to preoperative baseline value in patient

with high pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy, but it was not statistically significant.

There was rise in postoperative level of serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin in patients who underwent low pressure (10 mmHg) laparoscopic cholecystectomy, but it was not statistically significant. There was slight decrease in serum alkaline phosphatase level in postoperative period in this group of patients, but it was not statistically significant decrease.

In conclusion, the results show that 14 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum decreased the blood flow to the liver and increased postoperative 1st-hour serum AST, ALT and total bilirubin levels. It is therefore concluded that 10 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum is superior to 14 mmHg pressure pneumoperitoneum in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

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